

**LAGOS
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ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

Published by:

LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY, OJO
LAGOS STATE

www.eliteworksrp.com.ng/lasu/home.html

LAGOS STATE UNIVERSITY
LASU Journal of Management & Social Sciences

Volume 19 No. 2 July 2025

**LAGOS
STATE
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Journal of

**MANAGEMENT
AND
SOCIAL SCIENCES**

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

**Volume 19 No. 2
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**Published By
Lagos State University
Ojo, Lagos State**

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Ojo, Nigeria

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ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences is a multi-disciplinary journal published by the Lagos State University, Nigeria. Its major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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LASU Journal of Management and Social Sciences' major aim is to serve as rallying-point for intellectual brainstorming and to contribute towards the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria by providing a forum for ideas initiated and empirically tested by research experts to be published for the benefit of Policy Makers, Administrators and other functionaries in both the private and public sectors of the Nigerian economy.

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ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

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LASU JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

ISSN: 978-33424-4-4

Volume 19 Issue 2

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EFFECT OF INFLATION RATE ON DOMESTIC CAPITAL INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA 1988-2024

* Okeke, Damian Chibuike

** Anochie, C. Uzoma

*** Udodirim, Chukwuemeka

ABSTRACT

One of the major issues facing global economies has been inflation. As a result, policymakers have been struggling to give a long-term solution that will slow the pace of inflation and its effects on other macroeconomic indicators and economic sectors. Since policymakers were unable to determine the most effective way to manage inflation, hence, this study focused on the effect of inflation on gross domestic investment in Nigeria from 1988 to 2024. The effect of inflation, money supply, and interest rates on gross domestic investment in Nigeria is the study's main objective, which is constructed based on the empirical literature evaluated and relevant theories. The Vector Autoregressive approach was used to estimate and analyze data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria. The results show that gross capital investment in Nigeria is positively and negligibly affected by inflation. In a similar vein, interest rates in Nigeria have a favorable but insignificant effect on gross domestic investment. On the other hand, the money supply had a negligible detrimental effect on Nigeria's gross domestic investment. In light of the study's findings, the government, working with the relevant institutions, is advised to create clear, workable fiscal and monetary policies as well as economic reforms that will lower inflation and create a unique, welcoming atmosphere for both new and current investors in Nigeria. Additional investment that will result from this will result in extra job placement, increased consumption expenditure and in turn boost economic growth of Nigeria.

Keywords: *Inflation Rate, Capital Investment, Money Supply, Interest Rate, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

The formulation of effective macroeconomic policies that regulate key economic indicators such as interest rate, inflation rate, foreign exchange rate and unemployment to foster a serene environment for long-term investment and sustainable economic growth remains a significant challenge for many developing countries across the world (Umar & Mustafa 2021). In the current globalized world, this issue has grown even more complicated, with developing nations like Nigeria at risk of continued underdevelopment as a result of

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insufficient capital creation, an unsuitable policy mix, a trade imbalance, and an unfriendly investment climate according to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (2022). The inadequately designed regulatory framework has restricted business responsiveness to investment, misallocated resources from productive to unproductive investments, negatively impacted most macroeconomic indicators, diminished entrepreneurial enthusiasm, and constrained the nation's ability to generate employment opportunities (Nsonwu (2022).

Nigeria's economy descends into a period of slow economic activity marked by a higher inflationary rate, an unfavourable exchange rate, high unemployment, and interest rates because the country failed to design the right policy mix, and unable to effectively utilize her natural resources, to create an enabling business environment that would keep various macroeconomic indicators low to attract investors and create more job opportunities that would stimulate consumption spending (World Bank, 2023). External factors like the COVID-19 pandemic and an unfavorable balance of payments have made matters worse and caused Nigeria to shift from a production economy to a consuming one, according to the World Bank (2022).

Nigeria has implemented various monetary policies and economic measures to curb inflation, enhance infrastructure, and offer additional incentives to attract local investors and accelerate economic growth (Ibolor & Omehe 2022). For example, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), acting on behalf of the Nigerian government, has been using monetary policy tools to control inflation, such as raising the monetary policy rate (MRR), lowering the money supply, and adopting an inflation targeting benchmark and on November 26, 2024, the lending rate was increased from 25 percent to 27.50 percent, marking the sixth consecutive hike in 2024 (CBN brief December 2024). Furthermore, a number of economic reforms have been implemented, such as the Nigerian Agenda 2025, Vision 20:2020, and the Nigerian National Development Plan (NAP) (Uche 2019). All of these short- and long-term economic measures and reforms are intended to achieve fiscal produce, a low rate of inflation, and increased access to infrastructure that would guarantee sufficient local and foreign investors who could raise consumption spending, encourage savings, lower unemployment, and ultimately support Nigeria's economic growth (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2022).

The majority of macroeconomic indicators are still trending downward despite the Nigerian government's adoption of several monetary policies and national economic reforms through the proper authorities to lower excessive inflation and attract more investment (John & Obioma 2017). For example, as of the end of 2024, the dollar to Naira exchange rate was \$1 to N1650, and the interest rate climbed from 2.8 percent in 2012 to 27.9 percent in 2024, then inflation rate moved 14 percent in 2012 to 34.5 percent at the end of 2024, which was a record high in the last two decades CBN 2023). Over the past few decades, the rate of economic development has been erratic. Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product rate displayed notable fluctuation between 2014 and 2024, starting at 6.22 percent in 2014, then falling to -1.51 in 2016, before rebounding to 3.40 percent by 2024 (National Statistics Bureau of Nigeria, 2025). All of these led to a number of economic distortions, such as rising pricing for products and services, a decline in the population's standard of living, and excessive operating costs.

Numerous academicians who have undertaken empirical study on the effects of these macroeconomic indicators (inflation) on investment have failed to reach a consensus in their efforts to identify the path of these indicators' weakness and address it. Ejima and Emereni (2020) and Omedera (2020) that investigated on the effect of inflation on investment found that inflation has negative influence on investment, however Mogaji, Falade and Ogundipe (2020) and Olufemi, Omelede and Obasuji (2013) discovered in their studies that inflation

has a positive effect on investment. therefore, this indicates that the behaviour of inflation has become challenging to comprehend, particularly in Nigeria, as demonstrated by the inability of economic reforms and macroeconomic policies to reduce the high rate of inflation and the inability of earlier researchers to reach a consensus. This problem under discussion has inspired this study which sought to reinvestigate the effect of inflation on gross domestic investment in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of inflation on domestic capital investment in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives are to

- Assess the effect of inflation rate on domestic capital investment Nigeria.
- Investigate the effect of money supply on domestic capital investment in Nigeria.
- Analyse the effect interest rate on domestic capital investment in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are stated to guide the study

- There is no significant positive effect of inflation on domestic capital investment in Nigeria.
- Money supply has no positive significant effect on domestic capital investment in Nigeria.
- There is no significant positive effect of interest rate on domestic capital investment in Nigeria.

EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

This study's empirical literature analysis includes works by Olufemi, Omelade, and Obasuji (2013), Ojima and Emerenini (2020), and Mogaji, Falade, and Ogundipe (2020) that discuss how inflation affects domestic investment in Nigeria.

Olufemi, Omelade, and Obasuji (2013) examined how Nigeria's inflation rate affected investment levels between 1970 and 1986. To estimate and analyze the effects of GDP and inflation on investment in Nigeria, the study used the Vector Error Correction Model. According to the study's findings, the inflation rate and GDP both positively impacted the amount of investment in Nigeria. As a result, the government should implement aggressive policies that will significantly maintain the country's low inflation rate, which will encourage current investors and draw in new ones.

Omodera (2020) examined the effects of population, public debt servicing, inflation, currency rates, total government spending, and real GDP on government capital investment in Nigeria between 2000 and 2017. The results from estimating and analyzing the causal impacts of these independent variables on the dependent variable using the Ordinary Least Square approach showed that population and real GDP had no discernible detrimental effects on government capital spending. Additionally, Nigerian government capital investment is negatively impacted by inflation and public debt payments. On the other hand, government capital expenditures are significantly positively impacted by the exchange rate and overall government spending. According to the study's findings, the government should guarantee sufficient funding for capital projects and general infrastructure that can stimulate economic activity and accelerate Nigeria's economic growth.

Using the Ordinary Least Square method (OLS), Ojima and Emerenini (2020) investigated how interest rates and inflation affected investment in Nigeria between 1992 and 2018. The model of the study is divided into dependent variable (domestic investment), and the predictors (inflation rate and interest rate). The data revealed that inflation and interest rate have a negative and insignificant influence on investment. Hence the study proposed that monetary authority should create measures that will stimulate savings and cut prime lending rate to real investors. This will encourage more investment and in turn spur economic growth in Nigeria.

Mogaji, Falade, and Ogundipe (2020) used Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) to examine the impact of interest rates and inflation rates on domestic investment in Nigeria between 1986 and 2018. The model's variables include gross domestic investment, which serves as dependent variable, and the predictors, which included the money supply, inflation rate, interest rate, and governmental spending. The results showed that Nigeria's inflation rate significantly boosts domestic investment. Gross domestic investment is positively and negligibly impacted by interest rates. Furthermore, at the 5 percent level, the inverse link between government spending and domestic investment was negligible. The money supply has no discernible beneficial impact on domestic investment, according to additional examination of the results. Based on the study's findings, the government and policymakers should create policies that would support local investors, prevent a significant difference between the lending rate and deposit rate and keep inflation within a single digit.

Ezeibekwe (2020) examined the effect of inflation, Money supply on domestic investment from 1981 to 2018. The model of the study was divided into dependent variable (Domestic investment) and explanatory variables which include inflation and Money supply. Data collected were estimated and analysed econometric technique; Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The result revealed that the effect of interest rate on investment depends on the level of the inflation rate. In addition, the size of the effect of interest rate on investment gets weaker as the inflation rate increase. Further analysis revealed that the effect of the money supply on investment does not depend on the level of the inflation rate. Hence, it is recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should work to deepen the scale, capacity, and efficiency of its open market operation by ensuring that most of the people can participate with minimal transaction cost and by making different financial instrument.

Nsonwu (2022) looked at how macroeconomic factors affect Nigeria's gross fixed capital investment between 1981 and 2020. Gross fixed capital investment was one of the dependent variables in the model, and the exchange rate, inflation rate, and inflation were explanatory variables. Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was used to estimate and analyze the obtained data. The study's conclusions demonstrated that throughout the period under consideration, Nigeria's gross fixed capital formation growth rate was negatively impacted by inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates. Therefore, the research suggested, among other things, that the government and monetary authorities should implement policies that would maintain interest rates and inflation in the single digit range in order to stabilize other macroeconomic variables that might encourage investment in Nigeria.

It is evident from the evaluated literature that there aren't many works on the subject, and most of the literature reviewed are outdated and needs to be updated. By updating the study to 2024 and contributing to the body of literature, the study addresses the study's literature gap.

Theoretical Foundation of the Study

Neoclassical Investment Theory

The neo-classical theory of investment was used in the study. In 2020, Mogaji, Falade, and Ogundipe used the idea. According to Mogaji et al., three factors—interest rates,

inflation, and income—determine investment in an economy. Therefore, they use this theory to construct their model, which states that investment is a function of inflation, and interest rates, or $INV = f(\text{income, inflation, and interest rate})$. Their model is applied in this study with little modification. Hence the study's model is expressed as investment is the function of inflation rate, money supply and interest rate. The money is included since its volume influences the rate of investment via inflation and interest rates. This model's functional form is $INV (GFCF) = F(INFL, MS, INTR)$.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The methods and techniques used to accomplish the study goal are included in the research design (Koutsoyiannis 1993). Time series secondary data make up the data set for the variables. As a result, the study used an ex post facto research design. This is due to the fact that secondary data are pre-processed information that is hard for researchers to change. The Vector Regressive (VAR) approach was used to analyze data that was gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria.

Sources of Data

The Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) publications, including the 2018 and 2024 statistical bulletins, the 2025 CBN April quarterly brief, along with the Nigerian National Bureau of Statistics 2025 serve as the source of data for the variables

Model Specification

The research's model was created by examining a large number of empirical studies and ideas related to the field of study. The model is based on the work of Olufemi, Omelade, and Obasuji (2013) and Mogaji, Falade and Ogundipe (2020). Olufemi et al expressed investment as a function GDP and inflation rate, while Mogaji et al expressed investment as function of inflation and interest rate. The two models are modified by excluding GDP and adding an extra variable, money supply. Therefore, GFCF is expressed as the function of interest rate, money supply, and inflation rate in the research model. Interest rates are included since they are a major influence of fund borrowing and the cost of capital. The model is expressed as follows in both natural logarithm and econometric forms:

$$GFCF = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 INFL + \beta_3 MS + \beta_2 INTR + \mu$$

$$LGFCF = L\alpha_0 + \beta_1 LINFL + \beta_2 LMS + \beta_3 LINTR + \mu$$

Where: LGFCF is logarithm of gross fixed capital formation,

LINFL is logarithm of inflation,

LMS is logarithm of money supply,

LINTR is Logarithm of interest rate

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Result

Variables	Mean	Medium	Max.	Mini.	Std Dev.	Skewness	Kuitosis	obs
LGFCF	2.652480	2.824997	3.390658	1.366610	0.555246	-0.775153	2.577753	37
LINFL	20.83703	13.25000	72.84000	5.390000	17.47035	1.540530	4.179236	37
LMS	16.98216	14.79000	27.34000	8.460000	5.844723	0.127763	1.407532	37
LINTR	18.38622	17.59000	29.80000	10.50000	3.727730	0.863209	4.833538	37

Source: Researcher's compilation of e-view output 2025

The descriptive statistics of the four variables included in the GFCF model from 1988 to 2024 are shown in Table 1. The average values for Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF), Inflation Rate (INFL), Money Support (MS), and Interest Rate (INTR) are 2.652480, 2.83703, 16.98216, and 18.38622 respectively, while the medium values for

GFCF, INLF, MS, and INTR are 2.824997, 13.25000, 14.79000, and 17.59000. The results show that the interest rate has the highest average and middle values during the reviewed period, while inflation has the lowest average and middle values. The standard deviation, which accounts for discrepancy, shows that the standard deviation coefficient values for GFCF, INFL, MS, and INTR are 0.555246, 17.47036, 5.844723, and 3.727730, respectively. According to the results, GFCF has the lowest disparity and MS has the largest. The maximum value for GFCF, INFL, MS, and INTR was 3.390658, 72.84000, 27.34000, and 29.8000, respectively, while their minimum coefficient values were 1.366610, 5.39000, 8.46000, and 10.50000, according to the maximum and minimum descriptive statistics, which show the degree of individual variability among the variables. This suggests that, out of all the variables, GFCF recorded the least volatility and INFL the most.

The distribution's form is captured by the skewness. The result of skewness in table 1 reveals that the variables INFL, MS, and INTR have positive coefficient values of 1.5405301, 0.127765, and 0.863209, respectively, suggesting that they are tailed to the right. The variable GFCF has a negative coefficient value of -0.775153, indicating a leftward tail. With kurtosis coefficient values of 2.577753 and 1.407532, respectively, which are less than 3, GFCF and MS are platykurtic, whereas INFL and INTR are leptokurtic, with kurtosis coefficient values of 4.179236 and 4.833538, respectively. Kurtosis is a measure of how sharp a distribution's peak is. The research observation is 37 showing the number of years included in the model.

Unit Root Test

Using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller technique, all of the variables in the GFCF Model are evaluated to determine their stationarity qualities. The results of the unit root test at both level and first difference are shown in the table 2 below.

Table 2: Unit root test result at level and at first difference using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) approach

Variables	At Level			At First difference				
	Test statistics	0.05 % critical value	Level	Stationary or Not stationary	test Statistics	0.05 % critical value	Level	Stationary or Not stationary
LGFCF	-2.382276	-2.948404	1(0)	Not stationary	-3.819625	-2.951125	1(1)	Stationary
LINFL	-3.419057	-2.948404	1(1)	Stationary	-5.844762	-2.951125	1(1)	Stationary
LMS	-0.544342	-2.948404	1(0)	Not stationary	-4.455043	-2.951125	1(0)	Stationary
LINTR	-3.066740	-2.948404	1(1)	Stationary	-4.21188	-2.951125	1(1)	Stationary

Source: Researcher's compilation of e-view output 2025

The inflation rate (INFL) and interest rate (INTR) are stationary at level, as indicated by their ADF statistics values of -3.419057 and -3.065740, which are greater than their critical values at the 5 percent level of significance. This indicates that INFL and INTR are integrated of order 1(1). Based on the results in table 2 above, the money supply (MS) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) are not stationary at level, as indicated by their t-statistic values of -2.382276 and -0.544342 which are higher than their critical values of -2.948404 at the 5 percent level of significance. It is necessary to test every variable at first difference since all the variables are not stationary at level. At first difference, 11 of the variables GFCF, INFL, MS, and INTR had coefficient ADF statistics values of -3.829625, -5.844762, -4.455043, and -4.211888 (see table 2 above), which are higher than their critical values of -2.951125 at the five percent level of significance. According to the results, GFCF, INFL MS, and INTR are integrated in order 1(1) at first difference. The results of the unit test, as shown in Table 2, offer a solid basis for submitting the variables to a co-integrating test in order to ascertain whether or not there is a long-term link between them.

Johansen Co-Integration Test Result

Table 3 below shows the findings of the cointegration of trace statistics and Max-Eigen statistics, which are performed based on Jeselius and Johansen's techniques to ascertain the long-run equilibrium connection among the variables

Table 3: Unrestricted C0-integrated Rank Test (Trace)

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: LGFCF LINFL LMS LINTR

Lags interval (in first difference)1 to 1

Unrestricted Co-integrated Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob**
None*	0.666926	70.44479	47.85613	0.0001
At most 1*	0.407787	31.96585	29.79707	0.0277
At most 2	0.211596	13.62976	15.49471	0.0937
At most 3*	0.140735	5.308708	3.841466	0.0212

Unrestricted C0-integrated Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob**
None*	0.666926	38.47893	27.58434	0.0014
At most 1	0.407787	18.33609	21.13162	0.1178
At most 2	0.211596	8.321052	14.26460	0.3470
At most 3*	0.140735	5.308708	3.84166	0.1212

Trace test indicates 2 co-integrating equations at 0.05 level

*Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**Mackinnon –Haug-Michelis (199) P-values

Source: Researcher's compilation of e-view output 2025

From the result in table 3, trace statistics and eigenvalue statistics show three and two co-integrating equations, respectively, at a five percent level of confidence. Trace statistics values at none (GFCF), at most 1 (Inflation rate) and at most 3 (interest rate) are 70.44479, 31.96585 and 5.308708 which are higher than their five percent critical values of 47.85613, 29.79707 and 3.844146 in that order. The maximum Eigen statistics values at none (GFCF) and at most 3 (INTR) are 38.47893 and 5.308708, respectively, which are higher than their five percent critical values of 27.58434 and 3.841466. The unit test of mixed order and the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship among the variables restore the confidence to move forward using Autoregressive estimates for estimation and analysis of the GFCF model.

Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Estimates

The estimated coefficient values for explanatory variables, including inflation rate, money supply, and interest rate are displayed in table 4 below.

Table 4: Result of the Vector Auto-Regression Estimates of Effect of Inflation, Money Supply and Interest Rate on Gross Domestic Investment

Dependent variable D(GFCF)

Independent variables LINFL LMS LINTR

Standard errors in () & t-statistics []

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistics
LINFL (-1)	0.001004	0.00240	0.41843
LMS(-1)	-0.012519	0.01529	-0.81884
LINTR(-1)	0.007959	0.00778	1.02286
C	0.062424		

R-Square = 0.934377; Adjusted R-Square = 0.914185; F-Statistics 46.27523

Source: Researcher's compilation of e-view output 2025

The results in table 4 above show that the inflation rate coefficient value at lag one is 0.001004, which is positive, and that the related t-statistics value is 0.41843, which is lower than the t-tabulated value of 2.043. This finding suggests that the effect of inflation on gross fixed capital creation is positive but negligible. Conversely, the money supply (MS) coefficient value is -0.12579, which is negative, and the t-statistic is -0.81884, which is smaller than the t-tabulated value of 2.042. The result suggests that the money supply has a non-significant and negative effect on gross fixed capital creation. The interest rate has a positive and negligible impact on Nigeria's gross capital creation, according to the coefficient value of 0.007959 at lag one and the t-statistics value of 1.42286, which is lower than the student t-test value of 2.043. The constant (C) has a positive value of 0.062424. This finding shows that GFCF increased by 6.2 percent over the examined period when these predictors—INFL, MS, and INTR—were not included in the model.

The model's predictors, INFL, MS, and INTR, accounted for roughly 93% of the variation in the dependent variable (GFCF), according to the R-Square, which comes out at 0.934377. Other variables that were not taken into consideration were responsible for the remaining 7% of the variation. This outcome shows how well the model fits. At the 5 percent level of significance, the explanatory variables INFL, MS, and INTR are statistically significant, according to the f-statistics, which measure the combined significance of the explanatory variables. The coefficient value of 46.27523 is higher than the f-tabulated.

Post Diagnostic Test

The purpose of the post diagnostic test is to ascertain if the model is appropriate and reliable, as well as whether it complies with the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) assumptions. The VAR Residual test, VAR Residual normality test, and VAR Residual serial correlation test are performed to accomplish this goal. The VAR residual test is used to determine whether Heteroscedasticity is present in the model, the VAR residual normality test employs Cholesky, and the VAR residual serial correlation test is used to determine whether autocorrelation is present. Table 5 below displays these three results:

Table 5: Post Diagnostic Test Results

VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Test (Autocorrelation)			
F-statistics	Df	Probability	
33.98309	16	0.0559	
VAR Residual Normality test (joint Jarque-Bera test)			
Components	Jarque –Bera	Df	Probability
1	1.033588	2	0.5964
2	15.86835	2	0.0004
3	0.322527	2	0.8511
4	3.732320	2	0.1547
Joint	20.95678	8	0.0073
VAR Residual Heteroscedasticity test (Levels & Squares)			
Joint test	Chi-square	Df	Probability
	178.6686	160	0.1488

Source: Researcher's compilation of e-view output 2025

The LM test indicated no significant autocorrelation in the residual (the p-value of 0.0559 is greater than the 5 percent critical value), according to the post regression result test shown in table 5 above. This suggests that the model captures the relationship between the variables without autocorrelation. The result of the Heteroscedasticity test indicates a p-value of 0.486 and a chi-square value of 178.66861. This finding suggests that the p-value is higher than the crucial value of 0.05, indicating that the Null hypothesis—that there is no Heteroscedasticity—is accepted. The model's dependability for economic forecasts is confirmed by the lack of autocorrelation and Heteroscedasticity. The joint Jarque-Bera has a

value of 20.95678 and a p-value of 0.0073, which is less than the 5 percent critical threshold, indicating that the model's residual is normally distributed. This indicates that the data set used for the study is drawn from normal distribution.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Unit root and cointegration tests were performed prior to the Vector Auto regression (VAR) model estimation. A combination of stationarity at level and stationarity of all the variables at first difference is found by the unit root test result. In particular, at the level the variables, INFL and INTR are not stationary, although GFCF and LMS are. All of the variables are stationary at first difference. The data are put through a co-integration test with a mix of stationarity of all variables at level and first difference. Five co-integrating equations are shown by the cointegration test, indicating that the variables in the VAR model have a long-term connection.

Table 4 shows that the coefficient value of the inflation rate LINFL(-1) at lag one is 0.001004 based on the vector auto-regression estimations. The student t-tabulated value of 2.042 is less than the t-statistics value of 0.41843. The outcome suggests that Nigeria's gross domestic investment is positively and non-significantly affected by the inflation rate. This means that gross domestic investment rises by around 0.10 percent for every unit increase in the inflation rate. The economic implication of this result is that inflation drift from 1988 to 2024 encourages domestic investors to invest in Nigeria. Put another way, throughout the time under consideration, the rate of inflation promotes economic activity through increased investment, which result in higher production and economic growth. This outcome is consistent with the findings of Mogaji, Falade, and Ogundipe (2020) and Olufemi, Omelade, & Obasuji (2013) that came to the conclusion that inflation had a beneficial impact on gross domestic investment in Nigeria.

The money supply (MS) coefficient value at lag one is -0.012519, with a t-statistics value of -0.81884, which is lower than the student t-tabulated value of 2.042. According to these finding, Nigeria's money supply has a negligible and adverse effect on gross domestic investment. According to this conclusion, total domestic investment is reduced by around 0.12% for every unit increase in MS. The economic ramification of this finding is that, over the reviewed period, the money supply grew more quickly than the economy's capacity for production, which raised prices, decreased money's buying power, and perhaps deterred investment

At lag one, the interest rate coefficient value is 0.003133. With a t-statistic of 1.02286, below the student t-tabulated value of 2.042, indicating that inflation rate has a negligible beneficial effect on Nigeria's gross domestic investment. According to this finding, gross domestic investment increases by around 48.9 percent for every unit increase in interest rates. This has the economic consequence of encouraging domestic investors to borrow money from financial institutions for investment purposes as lending rate encouraged such. This is because the future revenue stream from investments made with borrowed funds is greater than the cost of capital. The increase in investment leads to more job creation which in turn boosts economic expansion.

The coefficient value of constant (C) was 0.062424, meaning that gross domestic investment rises by around 6.2 percent when all explanatory variables, including LINFL, LMS, and LINTR, remain constant. The implication of this result is that there are other variables that effects gross domestic investment that are necessary but are excluded in this model. However, these variables are accounted for by the stochastic variable.

The R^2 value of 0.934877 indicates that the explanatory variables LINFL, LMS, and LINTR accounted for about 93.4 percent of the changes in the dependent variable, GFCF, with additional factors not included in the model accounting for the remaining 6.6%. The outcome shows that the model is both desirable and fit. This finding has the economic implication that every variable in the model does its best job of describing changes in the dependent variable. The high p-value of 46.27523, which is more than the 0.05 critical value, indicates that the f-statistics, which describe the cumulative importance of the explanatory variables included in the model, are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The outcome demonstrates that policies and actions used to guide and manage the money supply, interest rate, and inflation rate had an effect on gross domestic investment in Nigeria over the reviewed period.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

- The results indicate that Nigeria's gross domestic investment is positively and negligibly affected by inflation. In light of this finding, the study suggests that in order to stimulate more investment, the government should concentrate on keeping inflation low and steady. A combination of fiscal and monetary policies that maintain inflation at a single digit and provide incentives and tax breaks for both new and current investors can accomplish this. This would intensify economic activity and hasten Nigeria's economic expansion.
- Money supply has a negligible and negative effect on Nigeria's gross domestic investment. Therefore, the study recommends that government, through the Central Bank of Nigeria, enact policies that expand the money supply to the point of reducing interest rate, thereby stimulating investment and placing more disposable income in consumers' hand to boost spending and investors will respond by expanding businesses and ramping up production to meet demand.
- Interest rates have a negligible beneficial effect on gross domestic investment, according to the study's findings. Therefore, in order to further encourage investment and economic growth in Nigeria, the government should keep interest rates the same or slightly decrease them.

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